

Supplementary Material S4 – Inter-item Correlation Analysis

...submitted to the Journal Paper “*Mapping Stakeholder Perspectives for Sustainability Transitions: The Case of Lithium-ion Battery Recycling*” by Rutrecht et al. published at Sustainability Journal of MDPI in 2025.

Inter-item Correlation Heatmaps

To complement the internal consistency analysis based on Cronbach’s α , **Pearson inter-item correlations** were computed for all questionnaire dimensions (opportunities, risks, barriers, enablers) to validate literature-derived items. These matrices visualize the **linear associations between individual items** within each dimension and provide insight into potential item redundancy or conceptual spread.

Average correlation values, ranges, and interpretive notes are given below.

General note

All heatmaps are based on **Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r)** calculated pairwise across all respondents ($n = 21\text{--}26$, depending on completion rate).

The visualizations use a diverging color scale centered at $r = 0$ (blue = negative, red = positive correlation).

Diagonal elements (self-correlations) were fixed at $r = 1$ for reference.

Figure S4.1. Inter-item Pearson correlation heatmap for Opportunity Items

Summary statistics:

Mean $r = 0.19$ Range = $-0.59 \dots 1.00$

Interpretation:

The Opportunity items show **low to moderate inter-item correlations**, suggesting that participants differentiated clearly between various opportunity types.

The broad spread of correlation values indicates a **conceptually diverse item set** covering environmental, economic, and social opportunities.

The few high correlations ($r > 0.8$) point to minor overlaps between closely related items such as *energy efficiency* and *greenhouse gas reduction*.

Figure S4.2: Inter-item Pearson correlation heatmap for Risk Items

Summary statistics:

Mean $r = 0.25$ Range = $-0.31 \dots 0.76$

Interpretation:

The Risk items display **moderate internal coherence** with some strongly correlated pairs, particularly among economic and regulatory risks (e.g., *market loss, loss of financing*).

This pattern suggests a **systemic perception of risks**—respondents tended to rate different risk factors in a related manner.

The limited number of negative correlations reflects distinct conceptual contrasts between technical and organizational risks.

Figure S4.4: Inter-item Pearson correlation heatmap for Enabler Items

Summary statistics:

Mean $r = 0.35$ Range = $-0.24 \dots 0.84$

Interpretation:

The Enabler dimension shows **moderate to strong coherence** with several high pairwise correlations among managerial and organizational enablers such as *awareness, transparency, and knowledge exchange*.

The results indicate that these enablers are **perceived as interlinked mechanisms** rather than isolated drivers.

Overall, the moderate average correlation supports the construct’s **internal consistency** while still preserving differentiation across technological, strategic, and cultural factors.